

Table 2

Internet resources contribute to the formation of basic skills

Basic skills	Internet resources
writing	emails, blog articles
reading	slide texts, subtitles, articles in online magazines and blogs
listening	audio tracks, videos, podcasts
speaking	direct communication on Skype and other similar sites, teleconferences

Internet information resources contain, as is known, texts, audio and visual materials on various topics. However, in order for students not to get confused in a large amount of information of various kinds, there was a need to develop special educational Internet resources aimed at meeting educational goals. [5]

Thus, the use of resources of the Internet provides ample opportunities for teaching foreign languages. It can be used by teachers not only for developing skills of listening, reading, writing and speaking, but also for improving communication skills, linguistic and socio-cultural training of students.

In conclusion, the development of the foreign language cognitive-communicative competence can create conditions for the complex use of various cognitive strategies within the framework of solving communicative tasks and for the independent choice of a strategy for solving problem communicative situations in the new conditions of foreign language communication, taking into account the intercultural context, the development of regulatory mechanisms for communication and work with information, and the development of cognitive-communicative competence of high school

students plays an essential role in the modernization of education system of Kazakhstan.

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THE ROLE OF CRITERIA- BASED ASSESSMENT IN THE CONDITION OF UPDATING THE CONTENT OF SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article considers the issue of the transition of Kazakhstan's school education to the updated content. One of the changes in education system of our country is the criteria- based assessment that is used for the assessment of students` achievements. The implemented system of criteria- based assessment is aimed at the development of the student, increasing his/ her motivation to learn. The role of evaluation criteria and regular feedback, understandable for each student and his parents, becomes essential. The effectiveness of the reform of school education will largely depend on the readiness of Kazakhstani teachers to work in the condition of updated system of education, in connection with which the teacher's practice and his research activities become important.

Keywords: criteria- based assessment, formative assessment, summative assessment, student`s achievement, school education.

In this modern world, there are a wide range of changes that are taking place in all fields of our life

which made an influence on the globalization of education, the expansion of economic, cultural and other bor-

ders of our country. In connection with the entry of Kazakhstan into the international educational space, there is a need to define the purpose of training and its functions in a new way. Today, in the process of daily learning, we need to develop the student's skills, skills and desire to learn throughout life in order to always be competitive. We must also teach him to study, thereby ensuring individual and independent work the student (according to the requirements of the Bologna Process), to focus the content and methods of teaching on competence. The development of humanity has acquired a global character, and this makes only a person who is able to live and act in such a space is competitive. Changes in the system of values that we want to see in our children are required. This should be the main incentive to quality learning instead of motivation by authoritarian pedagogy methods, and besides, it orients a person to maximum self-realization. In particular, already at school it is necessary to orient students on the desire to be successful in life.

In connection with the tasks set by the government, Kazakhstan made a complete transition to the updated content of training. It should be noted that the academic content has been preserved, and the expected results presented through the learning objectives system have changed. A distinctive feature of updating the content is that education will be built not from the content to the training, when the student must necessarily master the subject content that is laid down in the standard and programs, but from the expected learning outcomes. In this approach, the main thing is not the amount of students' knowledge on individual topics, but the real learning outcomes, as well as the skills and abilities of students to apply the received knowledge in real situations. At the same time, the main task of the teacher becomes the organization of such an educational space in which students switch to self-regulated learning. Within the framework of the updated educational standard, an integrative approach is widely used, which contributes to the formation of a holistic picture of the world due to the interrelation of content various academic subjects. The continuity of the content of education in the curricula of the subjects ensures the principle of "spiral". This principle establishes the following opportunity: each goal and topic of study after certain academic periods are reviewed repeatedly with a gradual deepening or complication of the volume of knowledge and skills on them.

Updating the content of school education is impossible without rethinking the school assessment system. According to B. McGowen, executive director of the joint project of the largest companies - Cisco, Intel and Microsoft, "the reform of knowledge assessment methods is extremely necessary for the implementation of any systemic changes in the field of education, and today we need not just changes, but transformations of a global nature" [1]. An extensive study has led to the conclusion that "most education systems do not keep up with the rapidly changing economy and do not provide students with the necessary skills.

If we analyze the state of Kazakhstan's system of assessing students' academic achievements in comparison with other countries, it should be noted that the

five-point assessment system provided for in Kazakhstan does not sufficiently reflect the level of students' knowledge, but it is not a generally accepted world system. That is why, one of the relevant approaches for Kazakhstan in the context of the transition to the updated content of education is the approach to assessing student achievements, which contributes to the positive overcoming of learning problems, individualization of the educational process, and in general, increasing educational motivation and the formation of self-regulation of students. It should be noted that the introduction of criteria-based assessment is focused on expanding pedagogical capabilities. And, first of all, for the effective application of the technology of criterion assessment of educational achievements the teacher needs to master the knowledge and skills of using such types of assessment as formative and summative.

The assessment system is an integral part of the content of education. It should be aimed at the correct choice of effective teaching methods and means by the teacher. But, what is the criteria-based assessment and its types within the framework of updating the content of school education in Kazakhstan? The term "criteria-based assessment" was first used by the American educator Robert Eugene Glazer in 1963. According to the author, criterion assessment is a process that helps to determine the correspondence between the achieved planned levels of educational achievements of students. Students are evaluated through predefined criteria. Criteria-based assessment excludes comparison and dependence of educational achievements of some students on the achievements of other students. According to Glazer, the concept of measuring achievements is based on the concept of a continuous process of acquiring knowledge: from complete lack of knowledge to ideal results. [2]

Let's consider modern theories of criterion assessment. Modern changes in the education system are determined by the humanitarian paradigm, a special role is given to the intellectual development of the student's personality, aimed at successful socialization and the development of functional literacy. The requirements for intellectual training presuppose mastering a set of cognitive competencies, the formation of which is possible in the process of sequential learning of thinking skills.

Questions about the importance of the relationship between formative and final assessment are reflected in the works of W. Charles (University of Bristol). According to scientists, the formative assessment and the final assessment were considered as serving two separate purposes. Formative assessment is aimed at improving learning. The summative assessment summarizes the results of the training at the end of the training period. However, in recent years, formative and summative assessments have been recognized as interrelated and complementary to each other. They can serve both purposes, depending on how teachers use assessment information and feedback. Studies show that teachers could make better use of assessment, taking into account this relationship. [3]

Formative assessment is also called assessment for learning, which is "the process of searching and interpreting data used by students and their teachers to determine the stage at which students are in the process of their learning, the direction in which they should develop, and determining how best to achieve the required level" [4]. Here we consider the idea that in order to improve the results of one's learning, it is necessary to respond to the feedback received, which, in turn, should determine motivation and desire to act. In this regard, the role of regular feedback, understandable for each student and his parents, becomes important. After all, formative assessment provides continuous feedback between the student and the teacher without assigning points and grades, and the student has the right to make a mistake and correct it. This makes it possible to identify problems in learning, adjust the learning process in a timely manner, and help achieve the best results.

The experience of some schools on the introduction of criteria-based assessment allows us to identify the relevance of this system of assessing students' academic achievements, because in this process the student's work is compared not with the work of classmates, but with a certain criterion, which gives him objectivity. There is a full involvement of students in the assessment process, as a detailed algorithm for deducing the final grade is provided, according to which each student can determine his own level of achievement. An important factor in assessing students is also the need to familiarize students with the evaluation criteria before completing the task and the availability of evaluation criteria for students during the task. The teacher should think about their location in the lesson in advance.

As we can see, the criterion assessment itself does not imply a process of competition between students or a comparison of their academic achievements. As we know, in traditional assessment, teachers are faced with a situation where parents disagree with the teacher's assessment, proving that the assessment is inconsistent with the knowledge of their children. In the context of the updated content of education, the fact of evaluating the educational activities of students according to predetermined criteria ensures transparency and accessibility for all participants in the educational process. Thus, each student has the opportunity to improve, reaching the level of their capabilities according to the specified criteria, and achieve the expected result in the subject. With the help of evaluation criteria, students learn to design a way to achieve their goals, and at the same time learn to more objectively assess the quality of their work.

Summative assessment is carried out to provide teachers, students and parents with information about the progress of students upon completion of sec-

tions/cross-cutting topics of curricula and a certain academic period (quarter/trimester, academic year, secondary education level) with scores and grades. This allows you to determine and fix the level assimilation of the curriculum content for a certain period and use the information obtained based on the results of summative assessment for planning, correction and analysis of the learning process. Teachers need to collect summative works of students completed in the process of summative assessment by sections and for a quarter in the student's portfolio. A portfolio is a means of recording, accumulating and evaluating individual achievements of a student during a certain period of his education. [5] Its role in the organization is undeniable the learning process aimed at the formation of functional literacy of the student. The portfolio can help in determining the directions of students' development, for example, when choosing a future profession, when consulting teachers or more qualified specialists in this field.

So, the updating of the educational paradigm has necessitated the introduction of a criterion technology for assessing the educational achievements of students in schools in Kazakhstan, which consists in comparing individual achievements of students with certain criteria for assessing the level of formation of the necessary competencies. At the same time, it is undeniable that the effectiveness of the implementation of the criteria assessment system in the country will largely depend on the readiness of society for this work, because the level of readiness of a school graduate for further professional activity depends not only on the school, but also on the social environment. In this regard, the requirements of the new education standards provide for the distribution of social responsibility for learning outcomes between educational organizations, parents of students and society as a whole.

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